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On the Development of the Northern Sea Route Communications System During Geopolitical Instability

KEYWORDS

Arctic economy,
Northern Sea
Route,
Arctic
enterprises,
investment
attractiveness,
mechanisms
of economic
development,
strategy
coordination

ABSTRACT

Introduction. The development of the Northern Sea Route (NSR) communications system has become increasingly relevant due to geopolitical instability. Expanding NSR infrastructure not only strengthens Russia's control over Arctic territories and transport corridors but also reduces dependence on external routes and enhances the security of cargo transportation.

Research objective. This study analyzes the pace of development of the NSR communications system in the context of regional geopolitical instability.

Materials and methods. The analysis draws on peer-reviewed articles, data on nuclear icebreaker development, and statistics on NSR cargo traffic (2020-2024). Methods include content analysis of official documents and international agreements, statistical data processing, comparison of alternative routes (the Suez Canal and the NSR), and modeling mechanisms to stimulate the Arctic economy and NSR development.

Results. Economic activity in the Arctic zone entails high operating and investment costs, which are generally feasible only for large, vertically integrated holdings. The development of Arctic territories therefore requires mechanisms that can stimulate investment and fully unlock the potential of the NSR. The study outlines an economic framework that links macro-, meso-, and micro-levels of the national economy, with the goal of enhancing investment attractiveness and successfully implementing large infrastructure and business projects in the Arctic region.

Conclusion. The proposed framework promotes the growth of the Arctic economy and the NSR by improving investment attractiveness and contributing to the socio-economic development of Arctic territories. Key factors include reducing investment risks, securing government guarantees and sectoral support, and lowering project costs through subsidized rates. The framework also facilitates access to international markets, technology transfer and innovation, and the expansion of Arctic infrastructure and logistics.

FOR CITATION

Received: Dec 17, 2024
Accepted: Mar 2, 2025
Published: Jun 1, 2025

Koshkarev, M. V., & Satmurzaev, A. A. (2025). On the Development of the Northern Sea Route Communications System During Geopolitical Instability. *Economic Consultant*, (2), 58–73. <https://doi.org/10.46224/ecoc.2025.2.4>

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INTRODUCTION

Relevance

Developing the Northern Sea Route communications system is important since it will strengthen Russia's control over Arctic territories and transport routes amid geopolitical instability, reduce reliance on external routes, and ensure the security of cargo transportation.

Creating alternative supply chains is vital for maintaining the stable supply of energy, raw materials, and goods. An effective communication system supports the development of Arctic resources, attracts investment, and drives infrastructure development – these factors are especially important during instability, when other regions may appear less attractive. Moreover, developing such system helps Russia strengthen its position in the international arena, demonstrate technological readiness, and highlight the strategic importance of the region. It also supports the country's participation in international Arctic projects, fosters dialogue with neighbors and partners, and promotes new forms of cooperation in a time of global instability. Overall, the development of the Northern Sea Route communications system is a strategic necessity for protecting Russia's national interests in the face of global change and regional challenges.

Literature review

The potential of the Northern Sea Route lies in its ability to shorten the time and reduce the cost of transporting goods between Europe and Asia, expand Arctic navigation, harness the region's rich natural resources, and stimulate the economic development of Arctic states.

S. Chuguryan et al. write that the length of the Northern Sea Route makes it economically and energetically significant and has considerable commercial potential for the transportation of oil, natural gas, and other fuels [1].

M. Li et al. note that NSR increases gross profit and reduces CO₂ emissions for tramp ship operators [2].

R. Zhang et al. argue that the accelerated melting of Arctic ice has led to increased navigation along the Northern Sea Route, thereby shortening the transport corridor between China and the European Union. The authors analyze various fuel-cost scenarios, including changes in fuel prices and ship speeds in ice conditions. According to their results, the NSR can lower transportation costs by 0.98% and

increase exports from China and the EU by approximately USD 14,986 million and USD 8,228 million, respectively [3].

J. Zhou et al. examine ConRo freight demand for Northern Sea Route transportation. Their results show that developing a long-term business strategy for ConRo shipping on the NSR, companies must balance several factors: capital expenditures for ice-class vessels, operating costs of such ships, and revenues from both contract and spot cargoes during NSR operations [4].

H. Ahmadzai notes that the Arctic region is undergoing significant changes in land and sea use, including fishing, forestry, transport, freshwater extraction, and urbanization. The author highlights both challenges and opportunities for sustainable use of Arctic resources associated with the mining industry and its supporting infrastructure. These challenges include both onshore and offshore resource development, such as plans for offshore and river field exploitation in fragile ecosystems [5].

Modernization of the Northern Sea Route requires developed port infrastructure, expanded icebreaker fleet, and improved navigation systems and technologies to ensure safe, year-round transportation.

N. Nevskaya publishes a number of official documents illustrating the application of Arctic policy to modernize the Northern Sea Route and its energy infrastructure. The researcher emphasizes the need for a systematic regulatory framework that harmonizes state documents such as strategic plans and federal laws governing Arctic development [6].

S. Chuy et al. note that the active development of digital technologies has significantly accelerated the pace of digitalization of logistics in general and sea cargo transportation specifically in the Arctic zone. The authors focus on the creation of infrastructure, specifically digital platforms, as well as the design and requirements of a digital ship system, digital project modeling, and the integration of these systems through cloud technologies and big data [7].

Competition and cooperation in the development of Arctic resources are interlinked: countries struggle for access to oil, gas, and minerals, but also participate in joint projects, scientific research, and regulation to ensure the safety and sustainable development of the region.

N. Didenko et al. note that currently, international competition for the possibility of using the Arctic Ocean as a shipping route and the development of Arctic

resources is intensifying. Scientists analyze the risks and challenges associated with the economic development of the Arctic, as well as possible scenarios for resolving territorial disputes [8].

D. Molloy observes that China is advancing its Belt and Road Initiative in nearby smaller states. The scientist notes that China does not declare any changes in its policy, the United States and Canada are slowly recognizing the impending threat, and the EU acknowledges the need for interaction and investment in the Arctic [9].

C. Jahn et al. identify the most critical factors in the development of the Northern Sea Route, such as a continuous presence in the Arctic, the development of NSR infrastructure, and cooperation with various countries. According to the researchers, qualitative development of the Arctic territories is impossible without the successful implementation of infrastructure projects [10].

A. Fadeev & M. B. Fadeeva examine the experience of developing hydrocarbon resources in the Arctic by the world's leading oil and gas powers to identify practical socio-economic approaches to resource development in the public interest and the potential prospects for their use in modern Russia. The authors discuss the interaction between the state and the oil and gas industry, and the formation of an effective strategy for managing hydrocarbon resource development [11].

Russia plays a key role in the development of the Northern Sea Route, investing heavily in infrastructure, icebreaker fleets, and navigation systems to make it an essential corridor for international cargo transportation and strengthen its strategic position in the region.

A. M. Golubchik & T. Sankauskas argue that the development of the NSR is a national strategic priority for Russia. The authors illustrate this using the example of liquefied natural gas transportation [12].

A. G. Kazanin et al. write that one of the main factors for achieving Russia's strategic objectives in the Arctic is the formation of a unified Arctic transport system, including the Northern Sea Route, which comprises sea and river fleets, aviation, pipelines, railways, roads, and coastal infrastructure (ports, navigation aids, hydrographic and hydrometeorological support, communications) [13].

R. R. Nogovitsyn et al. examine issues of assessing the budgetary provision of the Arctic regions of Russia with the goal of equalizing incomes and improving the well-being of local populations. The authors propose enhancing the involvement of mining companies in addressing socio-economic challenges in the Arctic territories

and supporting local populations through social investments by such companies in the regions where they operate [14].

V. A. Kryukov & V. I. Nefedkin write that a transition to a new institutional model is necessary, one in which Russia plays a leading role in shaping the forms and mechanisms for participation and interaction of all key stakeholders in Arctic projects through equitable dialogue and harmonization of the interests of the state, business, and local communities. The main challenges include the need to develop new skills and competencies for eco-social management and project execution, as well as increasing the readiness of personnel for effective dialogue and cooperation with local communities [16].

E. Carayannis et al. argue that the presence of significant oil and gas reserves on the Russian Arctic shelf does not guarantee the success of development projects, because a complex set of political, macroeconomic, and other factors influences their initiation and implementation. Economic, geopolitical, climatic, infrastructural, environmental, and other factors create uncertainty in Arctic oil and gas development [17].

E. G. Carayannis et al. propose an economic and socio-environmental framework for sustainable Arctic development, with particular emphasis on creating centers of economic growth through public-private initiatives aimed at the production and transfer of knowledge and innovation. Scientists have proposed the 'Five-Fold Spiral' model, which facilitates a mutually beneficial relationship among ecology, learning, and innovation, generating synergy between the economy, society, and democratic governance, providing a sound basis for sustainable development in the Arctic and the implementation of Arctic shelf projects [18].

K. S. Zaikov et al. provide examples of successful practices addressing common Arctic challenges, concluding that the "Arctic fever" phenomenon and the intensification of Arctic scientific partnerships through programs supporting technology and innovation implementation and the promotion of scientific stations at Arctic latitudes directly influence local development, stimulate economic progress, and establish new cooperation models [19].

A review of studies on the development and significance of the Northern Sea Route shows that the NSR's length and economic importance make it a promising route for transporting oil, gas, and other resources. Significant attention is given to changes in the Arctic related to resource development, fisheries, and infrastructure, as well as to sustainable regional use considering environmental risks.

International competition for Arctic resource utilization and shipping routes is intensifying, while associated risks and territorial disputes emerge. At the same time, infrastructure development and international cooperation are recognized as essential for the development of the NSR, without which the effective exploitation of Arctic territories would be impossible.

The development of the NSR is an essential national strategy for Russia, especially in the context of liquefied natural gas transportation and establishment of a unified Arctic transport system, encompassing various modes of transport and supporting infrastructure. New institutional models of interaction between the state, business, and local communities are required, taking into consideration political, economic, and environmental factors affecting resource development.

In light of the above, the authors formulated the research objective: to analyze the pace of the NSR communications system development during geopolitical instability in the region.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Scientific articles from peer-reviewed journals were used as materials, including: *Annals of Operations Research*; *Maritime Economics & Logistics*; *Mineral Economics*; *Studies on Russian Economic Development*; *Journal of the Knowledge Economy*; *Russian Economic Bulletin*; *International Journal of e-Navigation and Marine Economy*, and others. Analytical materials were data on the development of nuclear icebreakers with regard to their service life, as well as statistics on cargo transportation along the NSR in 2020-2024.

Research methods included content analysis of official documents, strategies, and international agreements; collection and processing of freight, infrastructure, and investment statistics; comparative analysis, in particular, comparison of navigation characteristics through the Suez Canal and the NSR, exemplified by the Yokohama-Hamburg route; and modeling mechanisms to stimulate the development of the Arctic economy and the NSR.

RESULTS

Over the past decade, the global economy has grown increasingly fragmented. China's rise as a superpower in the early 2010s coincided with the weakening of the G7 after the 2007-2009 financial crisis and Beijing's successful pushback in its

trade war with the United States, which saw China as a serious competitor. The rise of this new financial center created uncertainty, later deepened by the COVID-19 pandemic, armed conflicts in Ukraine and the Middle East, and mounting geopolitical tensions. Together, these shocks fractured the global economy further and reshaped its workings, especially in trade routes, logistics chains, and payment systems [20]. The International Military Conflict Index and the Trade Policy Uncertainty Index, shown in Figure 1, illustrate how fears about the economic fallout of war have pushed trade policy uncertainty higher. According to IMF estimates, index values rose sharply after 2022 [21].

Figure 1 Geopolitical risks reflected in indices of international military conflicts and global trade policy uncertainty. Compiled by the author using the Trade Policy Uncertainty Index and the Uppsala Conflict Data Program (UCDP)

Rising geopolitical instability has accelerated the restructuring of global logistics and production chains. The first warning sign was the imbalance in global container shipping caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. Another key factor in international logistics is the need to adapt sea routes linking the West and East to new geopolitical realities. Fighting in the Middle East and Houthi attacks on commercial vessels have raised risks for ships passing through the Suez Canal, driving up insurance rates. At the same time, the management of the NSR (which is a key northern corridor from Europe to Asia that largely runs through Arctic waters of the Russian Federation) has been reshaped. Table 1 compares comparison of these two main routes.

Table 1

Comparison of navigation characteristics on the Yokohama-Hamburg route via the Suez Canal and the NSR. Compiled by the author based on [22]

Comparison component	Yokohama-Hamburg route	
	Route via Suez Canal (SC)	Northern Sea Route (NSR)
Distance, nautical miles	11,585	7,356
Fuel consumption	High	Low
Travel time at cruise speed of 15 knots	32 days	18 days
Required speed for 32-day transit	15 knots	8 knots
Piracy threat	Yes	No
Passage fee	Low	High
Transportation costs (USD/TEU)	High	Low

The key advantages of navigation through the NSR are significantly shorter transit times, with the distance reduced by 36%, enabling fuel savings of about \$0.5 million for dry cargo ships of the MV Nordic Barents class [23], a time saving of 14 days, and a lower overall transportation cost. In addition, navigation through the Suez Canal carries piracy risks. A major drawback of using the NSR for transit flows is the need for ice navigation, which results in higher passage fees and seasonal climatic restrictions that can prevent NSR use in some months, depending on the annual ice conditions.

We note the following key factors in the changing significance of the NSR today:

- Shifts in the geopolitical balance, including unprecedented international sanctions against Russia, have significantly reduced cargo transport along the western, most developed segment of the NSR, particularly from Murmansk, Arkhangelsk, Onega, Kandalaksha, and Sabetta to European ports.
- The need to expand trade with friendly Asia-Pacific countries drives development of the eastern NSR infrastructure, especially supporting ports such as Pevek, Provideniya, Egvekinot, Anadyr, and Bering.
- The NSR's domestic significance is growing, encompassing civil logistics, transport infrastructure development (including the mainland railway), and ensuring Russia's strategic defense capability.

Accordingly, the following strategic development tasks for the NSR are identified:

- Expanding the icebreaker fleet and actively constructing and commissioning specialized ice-class vessels (gas carriers, tankers, container ships, etc.).

- Developing supporting port and coastal infrastructure and improving year-round communication and navigation systems.
- Promoting Arctic enterprises, supporting and subsidizing investment projects, and implementing sustainable development strategies for key industry players in the Arctic.
- Intensifying international cooperation in logistics and investment, building global value chains using NSR infrastructure and capabilities.

Icebreaking is required on the NSR for 8-10 months of the year, which raises passage costs compared with the Suez Canal. Russia possesses the world's only nuclear icebreaker fleet, currently consisting of 8 vessels (see Fig. 2).

The major renewal of the icebreaker fleet with Project 22220 universal nuclear icebreakers and the planned commissioning of the lead super-icebreaker Russia (Project 10510 Leader) in 2030 ensures reliable support for growing cargo volumes and increased ship traffic along the NSR for at least a 30-year horizon. Cargo transport data for 2020-2023 (see Table 2) show a steady 6% annual increase in total cargo volume. In 2024, the total reached 80 million tons, rising to 150 million tons in 2025 [24].

Figure 2 Development dynamics of nuclear icebreakers over their service life. Compiled by the author based on [24]

Table 2

Cargo transportation volumes along the NSR for 2020-2024.

Compiled by the authors based on [24]

Indicators of NSR use	2020	2021	2022	2023
Number of vessels, pcs.	497	712	726	412
Gross tonnage of vessels, million. tons	34.9	49.0	39.0	54.9
Volume of cargo transportation, million tons	33.0	34.9	34.1	36.3

An interesting pattern is observed in 2023 – the total gross tonnage of ships increased by 41%, and the number of vessels decreased by approximately 43%. Thus, the average carrying capacity of ships following the NSR route increases by 48%, and, therefore, emphasizes the importance of equipping the port infrastructure of the Arctic coast. The construction of ice-class ARC7 vessels has intensified; these include tankers that provide year-round export of oil from the Novoportovskoye field [25], gas carriers of the Yamal LNG project, supply vessels for production platforms, and diesel icebreakers [26]. The leaders of cargo transportation are Novatek (LNG), MMC Norilsk Nickel, and Gazpromneft. Since 2022, the structure of cargo transportation has changed – the volume of LNG transportation has increased, while transit traffic primarily to and from European ports has decreased.

In 2023, within the framework of the state corporation Rosatom's area of responsibility, work was completed and the LNG terminals and SGC Utrenny facilities at the port of Sabetta were commissioned. The volume of excavated soil during the dredging of the passage channel of the Utrenny Terminal exceeded 24 million cubic meters. Work was completed on the construction of the Southern and Northern ice protection structures and the border control point. The following investment projects were launched:

- Port Bay North oil terminal;
- Sea terminal at Cape Nagleynyn in the Pevek seaport;
- Reconstruction of the navigable passage channel in the Ob Bay of the Kara Sea ('Sea Canal');
- Projects to ensure navigation and digitalization of NSR infrastructure communications;
- Construction of the lead ice-class hydrographic pilot vessel ARC7.

The key to realizing the extremely high economic potential of the NSR lies in the creation and systematic development of transport and logistics hubs, including gas,

oil, container, and coal facilities. The presence of such accumulating infrastructure will ensure the year-round, uninterrupted operation of the NSR, mitigating harsh and unpredictable winter navigation conditions. These hubs will serve as collection points for hydrocarbons from tankers and gas carriers, as well as containers from Class ARC7 container ships. At these hubs, cargo will be transferred to larger vessels without ice reinforcement systems [27].

Such hubs will also be of critical logistical importance for key mining enterprises in the Arctic zone, primarily enterprises of the holdings of PJSC MMC Norilsk Nickel, PJSC AK Alrosa, Severstal, and Rusal. The Russian Arctic is a resource-rich region, producing about 10% of Russian oil, 83% of gas, more than 40% of global palladium (95% of Russian reserves), 20% of nickel (75% of Russian reserves), 10% of platinum (95% of Russian reserves), and 2% of cobalt (55% of Russian reserves).

Mining enterprises have several business features that determine higher requirements for management system efficiency. Primarily, this is the high capital intensity of production, due to the need to operate complex mining equipment at mines and quarries, processing plant machinery, and vehicles used in extraction. In addition, the efficiency of mining enterprises is influenced by factors such as underestimated product forecasts, continuous growth in operating costs, the need to ensure environmental safety, risks in occupational health and production safety, and fluctuating demand for finished products. The harsh Arctic economic conditions further amplify the complexity of mining and increase the demands on managing all processes along the mining value chain efficiently. A study by McKinsey analysts notes that over the past 15 years, operating costs for the extraction of mineral raw materials have grown by 90%, capital expenditures have increased by 33%, while profitability has declined by more than 28% [28].

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The last decade of development of enterprises in the Arctic zone has shown that only the largest vertically integrated holdings are successfully adapting to the digital transformation of key mining and processing operations. High investment costs in the Arctic region effectively create an insurmountable barrier for small and medium-sized enterprises, which could otherwise strengthen competition and increase the feasibility of complex investment projects with unique personnel skills and innovative technologies.

To strengthen the investment attractiveness of the Arctic region, we propose the following economic mechanism, which engages all levels of the national economy

(macro, meso, and micro) and extensively applies the concept of public-private partnership (see Fig. 3). The macro level of the proposed concept involves the coordination of NSR and Arctic economic development strategies with the full set of stakeholders: government agencies, enterprises and corporations with state participation, and the largest private companies shaping the Arctic economy.

Figure 3 Mechanism for stimulating the Arctic economy and the NSR

At this stage, negotiations should also include all key potential investors, including partners from friendly countries. A strategy reached through fair compromise serves as the basis for forming a pool of strategic activities, which must be formalized into concrete policies. Federal bodies form two main structures responsible for implementing the agreed strategy: the Coordination Center for NSR Infrastructure and the Intersectoral Competence Center. The first addresses coordination challenges for NSR development projects, including logistics hub expansion. The Intersectoral Competence Center coordinates and exchanges expertise, supports best practice implementation, and facilitates the transfer of technological and organizational solutions across enterprises in all Arctic industries.

At the meso level, programs from the NSR Coordination Center and Intersectoral Competence Center are broken down into territorial Arctic clusters, which share a similar level of socio-economic, transport, and technological development.

Target indicators for achieving the strategy of each territory are, in turn, broken down by the industries in each region. The key bodies responsible for implementing the agreed strategy at the meso level are state corporations, primarily Rosatom and Rostec, industry competence centers, and regional infrastructure entities, together ensuring conditions for achieving strategic goals while considering industry and territorial specifics.

At the micro level, enterprises within and across different territorial clusters form value chains. Each value chain has a goal-setting system derived from the macro level, taking into account the sub-goals and tasks at the meso level. Alongside the leading enterprises of the Arctic economy, value chains within the open innovation framework should include innovative small and medium-sized enterprises that provide both resources and research support.

Strategy indicators at the meso and micro levels serve as financial and economic covenants. When the minimum required level of each balanced set of indicators is achieved, access to limited resources is granted; for individual enterprises, this includes subsidized interest rates on investment loans, access to advanced technologies, and participation of research teams in key innovative projects with intellectual property rights retained. At the meso level, territories and clusters meeting an aggregated set of indicators receive priority state and project funding, grants, and increased transfers under targeted programs.

The mechanism for stimulating the Arctic economy and the NSR includes feedback loops—during value chain operations, information on achieved targets and obstacles

is continuously reported to higher levels. Analysis of target achievement forms the basis for adjusting strategy goals and, in case of critical deviations, serves as the basis for revising the main development strategy.

This mechanism enhances investment attractiveness and stimulates socio-economic development of the territories by:

- reducing investment risk through a three-level national economic mechanism;
- securing actual state guarantees for meeting declared investment obligations;
- providing extensive cross-industry support for competencies during project implementation;
- lowering discounted project costs through subsidized rates and long investment horizons, provided that the required operational indicators and investment obligations are met;
- facilitating access to international markets through joint investment projects;
- transferring advanced technologies and innovations developed by intersectoral research teams, with rights to use intellectual results in other enterprise projects;
- developing NSR territories and infrastructure, improving logistics performance for raw materials and finished products of Arctic zone enterprises.

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The author have declared that no competing interests exist

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Editor: Daniela Antonescu. Romanian Academy (Romania)